

SIGNATURE OF PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR

Title of report

A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled, Multicenter Phase III Trial of Rosuvastatin (Crestor[®]) 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Events Among Subjects with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein

I agree to the terms of this study protocol. I will conduct the study according to the procedures specified herein, and according to the principles of Good Clinical Practice (GCP) and local regulations.

Centre No.: <<>>

Signature:
<<(Name, title/position and address) >> Date

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Clinical Study Protocol: Appendix B

Study Code 4522US/0011

Version No. 2.0

Appendix Date 15 January, 2003

Appendix B

Sample written informed consent form

1. SAMPLE WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FORM

TITLE: A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled, Multicenter, Phase III Study of Rosuvastatin (Crestor[®]) 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Events Among Subjects with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein

PROTOCOL NUMBER: 4522US/0011

SPONSOR: AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP
1800 Concord Pike
Wilmington, DE 19850-5437

PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR:

RESEARCH SITE ADDRESSES:

Introduction

You have been asked to participate in a clinical research study. Before you decide whether or not to be part of this study, you should understand enough about the risks and benefits to make an informed decision. This process is known as informed consent. This Information and Consent Form describes the purpose, procedures, possible benefits, and risks for the study. Once you understand the study, you will be asked to sign this form if you wish to participate. If you are currently participating in another research study, or have participated in a research study within 30 days of the first visit, you cannot take part in this study.

The study doctor for this research project is interested in your health and in the conduct of this study. The study doctor is being paid by AstraZeneca to conduct this study. Before entering this study or at any time during the study, you may ask for a second opinion about your care from another doctor who is in no way associated with this study. You are not under any obligation to participate in a research project offered by your doctor.

After the study has been explained to you and you decide to take part, you will be asked to sign this consent form, which gives permission for the study doctor to proceed with the tests, procedures and medications administered in this study. You will also be given a copy of the signed informed consent for your records. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw (leave the study) at any time without giving a reason.

Likewise, it may be decided by the study doctor that continuing your participation in this study is no longer in your best interest and you will be withdrawn from the study. Failure to qualify for the study will also not influence your subsequent care.

Read this information carefully and ask any questions of the study doctor or the research staff before you sign this form.

Purpose of the Research Study

AstraZeneca is developing a drug, rosuvastatin, for the treatment of high cholesterol and is sponsoring this study. Rosuvastatin is an experimental drug that is not yet approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA). Rosuvastatin belongs to a group of drugs called “statins “ (statins are drugs that may help lower cholesterol levels). Several statin therapies are already available to you for lowering high blood cholesterol.

We are doing this study to determine the safety and effectiveness of long-term therapy with rosuvastatin compared with a placebo (inactive pill). This is to determine whether this treatment would be effective in reducing the risk of cardiovascular events such as a heart attack, stroke, angina and other medical conditions using a daily dose of 20 mg in men and women like you, who have low to normal levels of Low Density Lipoproteins (LDL) and cholesterol, but with elevated levels of C-Reactive Protein. Lipoproteins are “fat” molecules that are found in the blood which when increased in levels are thought to be associated with the blockage of arteries. C-Reactive Protein (CRP) is a clinical marker of generalized body inflammation without symptoms. In other studies with CRP, it has been shown that if you have high levels of CRP, you may be at risk for future cardiovascular events such as a heart attack, stroke, angina and other medical conditions that are associated with “hardening or blockage of the arteries” known as atherosclerosis or arteriosclerosis.

About 15,000 other subjects like you, in approximately 500 sites in the USA, will take part in this study. All participants will have periodic visits to the clinic for a period of about three and a half years. Rosuvastatin has already been given to more than 5,000 subjects in other clinical studies, in doses up to 80 milligrams a day and has been shown to lower cholesterol levels. Other studies have shown that the side effects of rosuvastatin are generally mild to moderate in intensity and short lived.

In other studies of over 8,000 patients with high levels of CRP, statin therapy has shown to have a greater benefit in those individuals with high CRP levels and has also lowered CRP levels even when you do not have high lipid or cholesterol levels.

Description of the Research Study and Procedures

Your participation in this study will be for a minimum of 36 months, during which time you will be asked to visit the clinic for approximately 11 scheduled visits over the length of the study (5-6 of the visits are scheduled within the first year). The number of procedures will vary at each visit.

During the **Initial Screening Visit**, you will visit the study doctor's office for initial testing. Before any procedures are carried out, you will be given the opportunity to read this Information and Consent Form and to ask any questions you may have. If you decide to participate, you will then sign this form and be given a copy for your records. A fasting blood sample will be taken at this time to determine whether or not you qualify to take part in the study. You will not be able to eat or drink anything except water for at least 8 hours before your visit to the clinic.

During the **Second Screening Visit** you will provide a fasting blood and urine sample and routine tests will be performed. You will not be able to eat or drink anything except water for at least 8 hours before your visit to the clinic. Also, a complete physical examination will be performed. Baseline data such as, information on your medical history, current medication use and health habits will be obtained. This will include information about your exercise and smoking patterns, family history of premature coronary disease and other associated conditions.

Immediately following the Second Screening Visit, you will be enrolled in a four-week '**Run-In Phase**'. You will be given study drug therapy to check if you are able to take study medication as prescribed in this clinical trial. If your lab tests and study drug compliance meet the requirements of the clinical trial, you will be scheduled for Visit 3.

Visit 3, the Randomization Visit, will be scheduled within 4 weeks of your Second Screening Visit. During this visit it is very important that you tell the clinic staff about all medications you are currently taking so that they can be recorded. You will be assigned to 1 of 2 treatment groups: rosuvastatin (20 mg) or to a placebo (inactive pill). The treatment group to which you will be assigned will be decided randomly (by chance). You have an equal chance (50%) of receiving rosuvastatin or a placebo. At each visit you will be given a study drug kit with enough medication to last until the next study visit. At Visit 3 and 4 you will be given 1 bottle of study medication and at Visit 5 onwards you will receive 2 bottles. You should take one tablet at the same time each day, as this will help you to remember. The bottles of medication will be labeled with instructions on how to take the tablets. You should take the study medication as instructed on the label and return all bottles and unused tablets to the clinic at every visit.

You will be scheduled to return in 13 weeks for **Visit 4** a follow-up **Safety Visit**. At this visit questions will be asked about your health since your last visit and a fasting blood and urine sample will be taken. That means that you will not be able to eat or drink anything except for water for at least 8 hours before your visit to the clinic. If your laboratory report indicates any unusual test results, you will be asked to discontinue the study medication. You will also need to tell the clinic staff about any other medications you are taking so it can be recorded.

You will bring your study drug with you during this visit. At the end of your visit, you will be given a new supply of the study drug.

You will be scheduled to return again in 13 weeks for **Visit 5**, your 6-month visit. At this visit a blood and urine sample will be taken. You will also bring your study drug with you to this visit. At the end of your visit, you will be given a new supply of the study drug.

All remaining study visits until the final visit will be scheduled every 6 months. During these visits, you will need to bring with you all the study medication bottles even if they are empty. A fasting blood and urine sample will be taken. At Visit 6, an additional blood sample will be taken for storage of plasma for future long-term analysis of cardiac inflammatory markers and/or safety issues. Questions about your health since your last visit will also be documented including all of the medications you are currently taking during your participation in this study. You will be given new supplies of your study medication before you leave the clinic.

At the Final Visit, you will need to return any study medication bottles you still have (even if the bottle is empty). A complete physical exam, an updated medical history and current medications will be recorded, and a fasting blood and urine sample will be taken.

One month after your last study visit, the research staff will telephone you to ask you how well you have felt since your last study visit to the clinic.

There are certain medications and food supplements that you are not allowed to take during the study. The research staff will review the medications and supplements that you cannot take during the study. If you are taking any of these medications, you will be asked not to take them during the study and, if necessary, an acceptable substitute will be suggested. If there is no acceptable substitute, you will not be able to participate in the study. Please make sure that you talk to the study doctor or research staff before you take any new medication or new supplements during the study.

You must be willing to attend all scheduled visits, take the study medication as directed and have the required tests and procedures done at each visit. For 8 hours before certain clinic visits, you will not be able to eat or drink anything except for water. If you have not fasted before a visit, you may be asked to return to the clinic within 2-3 days after you have fasted. The blood and urine samples will be sent to the central laboratory for evaluation.

You will be instructed to continue with your normal exercise routine for the entire length of the study. You should consult with the study doctor prior to beginning any new exercise routine.

The following procedures will be carried out at each study visit:

Visit 1 (Screening Visit)

- After you review this consent form and agree to participate in this research study, you will be asked to sign and date this Information and Consent form
- You will have blood taken from your arm to check your cholesterol level and determine whether or not you qualify to participate in the study. You may not eat or drink anything but water for 8 hours before this test.

Visit 2 (Screening Visit)

- You will be asked by the research staff to provide your detailed medical history. For your own safety, you must inform the doctor/research staff of all your past and present illnesses, allergies, medical conditions, and of all medications you are currently taking, including all over-the-counter preparations, and food or herbal supplements.
- You will have a complete physical examination that will include height, weight, pulse rate and blood pressure.
- You will have your waist measured.
- You will have blood taken from your arm to test your general health (called a full clinical chemistry and hematology), which include tests to determine liver and kidney function (you may not eat or drink anything but water for 8 hours before this test).
- You will be asked to give a sample of urine to check for infection and health of your kidneys
- Your doctor will ask you how well you have felt recently.
- Study drug will be dispensed to you with enough tablets for the following 4 weeks.

Visit 3 (Randomization)

- Your doctor will ask you how well you have felt since your last study visit to the clinic.
- You will be asked if you have taken any medications since your last visit.
- You eligibility will be confirmed.
- You will return your study drug container and a new batch of study drug will be dispensed to you with enough tablets for the following 13 weeks.

Visit 4 (Safety Visit)

- You will have blood taken to check your liver function (you may not eat or drink anything but water for 8 hours before this test).
- You will be asked to give a sample of urine to check for infection and health of your kidneys
- Your doctor will ask you how well you have felt since your last study visit to the clinic.
- You will be asked if you have taken any medications since your last visit.
- You will return your study drug container and a new batch of study drug will be dispensed to you with enough tablets for the following 13 weeks.

Visit 5

- You will have blood taken to check your liver function
- You will be asked to give a sample of urine to check for infection and health of your kidneys
- Your doctor will ask you how well you have felt since your last study visit to the clinic.
- You will be asked if you have taken any medications since your last visit.
- You will return your study drug container and a new batch of study drug will be dispensed to you with enough tablets for the next 6 months.

Visit 6 to 10 (every 6 months)

- You will have blood taken to check your liver function and your fasting cholesterol level at visits 6, 8 and 10 (you may not eat or drink anything but water for 8 hours before this test).
- You will be asked to give a sample of urine to check for infection and health of your kidneys

- Your doctor will ask you how well you have felt since your last study visit to the clinic.
- You will be asked if you have taken any medications since your last visit.
- You will return your study drug container at each visit and a new batch of study drug will be dispensed to you with enough tablets for the following 6 months.

If you require extended follow-up you will be asked to return at six-month intervals until study end. The assessments performed at visit 9 will be repeated at these visits.

Visit F (Final Visit)

- You will have blood taken to check your general health (called a full clinical chemistry and hematology), which include tests to determine liver and kidney function and your fasting cholesterol level (you may not eat or drink anything but water for 8 hours before this test).
- You will be asked to give a sample of urine to check for infection and health of your kidneys
- You will have a brief physical exam.
- Your doctor will ask you how well you have felt since your last study visit to the clinic.
- You will be asked if you have taken any medications since your last visit.
- You will have your waist measured.
- You will return your study drug container.

Risks and Inconveniences

Side effects of study medications

The study medication, rosuvastatin, like all medications, may cause side effects. You may experience none, some or all of those listed below. There may be unknown risks involved in taking this medication. Please advise the study doctor immediately of any unusual symptom(s) troubling you.

The side effects that have been previously reported with the study medication rosuvastatin have been usually mild and short-lived. The reported side effects are:

- myalgia (muscle pain or weakness)
- abdominal (belly) pain
- upset stomach (nausea)
- constipation
- liver abnormalities (increased liver enzymes)
- muscle abnormalities (increase muscle enzymes)

The study medication, rosuvastatin, may involve other risks including possible life threatening reactions that are unknown at the present time.

A rare side effect associated with statin medications is **rhabdomyolysis** (a rare life-threatening condition that occurs as a result of death of the muscle). Symptoms of rhabdomyolysis are muscle pain and weakness and, in some cases, rhabdomyolysis is associated with partial or complete shutdown of the kidneys. If the kidneys are affected, the urine output is reduced or absent and the color of the urine is dark. Another possible side effect associated with statin medications is **myopathy** (a condition that affects the muscles). The symptoms of myopathy include muscle weakness in the arms, legs, neck, muscle pain or tenderness, fatigue, and dark urine. You should discuss these side effects in more detail with your study doctor.

You should contact your doctor immediately if you develop unexplained muscle pain or muscle weakness, fever, fatigue, or if you don't feel well. You should stop your study medication if this occurs.

A very small number of subjects developed kidney failure while taking Rosuvastatin 80 mg/day. While these subjects had other illnesses and were on additional medications which could have caused renal damage, it is not possible to exclude the possibility that rosuvastatin may have contributed to the kidney failure in these subjects.

As with any medication, there may be other unknown side effects. If during the course of the study you experience any side effects, uncommon events or worsening of a condition you already have, you should immediately report them to the study doctor or research staff. If, in the judgment of the doctor, there is any problem(s) related to the study medication, the study doctor may decide that the study medication should be stopped, which means you will no longer participate in the study.

Blood Collection

Over the course of the study, no more than 200 milliliters of your blood (approximately 16 tablespoons) will be collected for testing. During this procedure you may experience

discomfort, pain, bleeding and/or bruising at the site of needle insertion. Occasionally, you may feel dizzy and or faint during the blood collection procedure. There is also a risk of infection called phlebitis (on rare occasion) or a hematoma (blood clot) that could develop at the site where the blood was collected.

Possible Drug Interactions

Potential Reactions with Blood-Thinning Medications such as Coumadin®(Warfarin)

The study medication, rosuvastatin, is known to sometimes interact with warfarin (often called by the brand name Coumadin®), a medication that slows down the blood's ability to clot and is sometimes referred to as a "blood thinner". If you are taking warfarin, there is a slight possibility that the study medication may increase the effect of warfarin, causing your blood to become too thin. You could have an episode of bleeding, which may take the form of bruising, a nosebleed, bleeding gums, or rarely, internal bleeding. If you are currently taking warfarin, or if you begin to take warfarin at any time during this study, you must inform the study doctor and your family doctor. If you notice any increase in bleeding or bruising, you should report this to the study doctor immediately. In order to reduce the risk of abnormal bleeding, the study doctor may order extra blood tests called the International Normalized Ratio (INR) to see if the effect of warfarin has been increased, causing your blood to become too thin. If this is the case, the study doctor may adjust your dosage of warfarin. INR blood tests will also be done just before and just after you receive rosuvastatin for the first time. INR testing uses one-teaspoon of blood each time the test is performed.

Any Antacid such as Maalox® or Amphojel® should be taken at least 2 hours after the dose of study medication to avoid the possibility of reducing the effectiveness of rosuvastatin.

New Information

You will be informed of any new information that becomes available on rosuvastatin, which may affect your decision to continue participation in the study.

Possible Benefits to You

You may or may not directly benefit from participating in this research study. It is possible that the risk of your chances of having a cardiovascular event may be decreased unless you receive placebo (inactive pill). Your study doctor cannot guarantee that you will benefit from your participation in this study.

In the future, other people like you could benefit from the results of this research. Information gained from this research could lead to improved medical care for them. However, your study doctor will not know whether there are benefits to people with low to normal levels of LDL-C and cholesterol but with elevated levels of CRP until all of the information obtained from this research has been collected and analyzed.

Alternative Treatments

You do not have to participate in this study to be treated for elevated levels of CRP. You are a healthy individual who does not need any form of treatment at this time except any that your primary doctor may prescribe.

Payment for Participation in Study

You will not receive any compensation for your participation in this study.

Costs of Participating in the Study

The study medication, study doctor's visits, and laboratory tests related to this study will be provided to you at no cost. Neither you, nor your insurance company will be charged for the study-related services provided during the course of the study.

Expenses for travel between the study clinic and your home may be reimbursed as described by the research staff.

Compensation for Adverse Events Resulting from this Study

If you experience any side effect or bodily injury, notify your study doctor immediately so that you can receive appropriate medical treatment.

If you suffer any adverse reaction or other physical injury resulting directly from the research study medication, AstraZeneca will provide reimbursement for the reasonable costs of medical treatment if:

- You took the study medication as instructed by your study doctor
- Your injury was not deliberately caused
- The study doctor was immediately notified about your injury
- You followed the medical advice of the study doctor

You will not be reimbursed for lost wages or other damages or losses or for medical expenses that have been covered by your medical or hospital insurance or by third party or governmental programs providing such coverage. No other form of compensation is available from AstraZeneca except remedies available under the law. Compensation for medical expenses is not an admission of fault or liability by AstraZeneca or anyone else.

Legal Rights

The above section does not restrict your right to seek legal assistance. You do not waive any legal rights by signing this Subject Information and Consent Form.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this study is voluntary. If you decide to volunteer for this study, the research staff will review this consent form with you and ask you to sign it. If you decide to participate in this research study you may discontinue at any time without giving a reason. You may refuse to participate or may withdraw at any time from this study without penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled.

Confidentiality

All study data will be kept confidential, however, authorized personnel from AstraZeneca, its representatives, the FDA, other Department of Health and Human Services agencies, government agencies in other countries, and the Independent Review Board may have access to the data. With your permission, your primary physician/family doctor (if you have one) will be informed of your participation in this study. _____ (*subject initials*)

To ensure confidentiality, you will be assigned a study number. The information collected during the study will be stored in a computer by your study number; your name will never be used. The study doctor, the study monitor, and any FDA/IRB reviewer will know that the information is related to you. The data and results from the study may be presented at meetings or published in medical literature, but your identity will not be revealed.

Publication of the results of the research

The results of this research may appear in scientific publications without identifying you in any way.

Records of Your Participation in this Research

The Sponsor will receive written reports about your participation in this research. Representatives of the FDA and the Sponsor may review your medical and research records kept here at **CLINIC NAME** to assure that the study is properly conducted according to applicable standards and guidelines. The FDA may photocopy your medical and research records to verify information submitted to the FDA by the Sponsor.

Contact for Questions

You have the right to ask questions about this study at any time and you are encouraged to do so.

If you have any questions about this study, contact the study doctor or the research staff at _____.

If you experience an injury you believe is related to this study, contact _____ at _____.

If you have questions about your rights as a research subject, you may contact [INSERT you LOCAL IRB NAME and PHONE NUMBER] An Institutional Review Board (IRB) is an independent group of scientific and non-scientific individuals who are responsible for assuring the community that the rights of participants in research are respected. They perform the initial and ongoing ethical review of the research study with the study subject's safety and welfare in mind. Members and staff of the IRB at this center may review the records of your participation in this research. A representative of the Board may contact you for information about your experience with this research. If you wish, you may refuse to answer any questions the representative of the Board may ask.

Right to Withdraw and Termination Procedures

You are free to withdraw from the study at any time. If you wish to do so:

- Please inform your study doctor immediately that you wish to withdraw from the research.
- Return to the research center for tests that may be needed for your safety.
- Return any unused study materials, including empty containers.
- Discuss your future medical care with your study doctor and/or your regular doctor.

If you withdraw from the study, it will not affect your future treatment and there will be no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled.

Your doctor, AstraZeneca and/or its delegates, or the FDA have the right to stop your participation in the study at any time, with or without your consent, for any of the following reasons:

- if you have an adverse effect from the study drugs;
- if you need a treatment not allowed in this study;
- if you do not keep your scheduled appointments;
- if you do not take the study drug as instructed;
- if you become pregnant;

- or if the study is canceled by the FDA or the Sponsor company.
- or for any other reason

Should your participation in the study be ended early for any reason, for your safety, it is your responsibility to do the following:

- Return to the research clinic for final laboratory tests, study assessments and examinations that may be needed;
- Discuss your future medical care with your study doctor and/or your primary doctor if needed;
- You must return any unused study medication and research study supplies, including empty containers to your study doctor.

INFORMED CONSENT STATEMENT

I, _____ (NAME OF SUBJECT), HAVE READ AND UNDERSTAND ALL THE INFORMATION OUTLINED IN THIS SUBJECT INFORMATION AND CONSENT FORM. I HAVE BEEN GIVEN THE OPPORTUNITY TO DISCUSS IT AND ASK QUESTIONS. ALL OF MY QUESTIONS HAVE BEEN ANSWERED TO MY SATISFACTION. I VOLUNTARILY CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN THIS STUDY. I UNDERSTAND THAT I WILL RECEIVE A COPY OF THIS INFORMATION AND CONSENT FORM.

BY SIGNING THIS INFORMATION AND CONSENT FORM I HAVE NOT WAIVED ANY OF THE LEGAL RIGHTS, WHICH I OTHERWISE WOULD HAVE AS A SUBJECT IN A RESEARCH STUDY.

I AUTHORIZE THE RELEASE OF MY MEDICAL RECORDS TO THE SPONSOR (INCLUDING ITS CONTRACTORS AND AGENTS), THE FDA AND OTHER GOVERNMENT AGENCIES IN THE US, CANADA AND OTHER COUNTRIES, AND THE [INSERT LOCAL IRB NAME] IRB.

Signature of Subject _____
Date of Signature (Month/Day/Year)

Printed name of Subject

Signature of Person _____
Date of Signature (Month/Day/Year)

Administering this Consent

Printed Name of Person

Administering this Consent

GENETIC TESTING ADDENDUM TO INFORMED CONSENT

Study Title:

A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled, Multicenter, Phase III Study of Rosuvastatin (Crestor[®]) 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Events Among Subjects with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein

Protocol Number:

4522US/0011

An optional part of this study involves the collection of a blood sample from you for genetic (DNA) testing. This testing may be used to help understand the relationship between genetic markers and diseases, to help develop new drugs and for other purposes. The samples collected will be stored so that other tests can be carried out in the future.

There is no direct benefit to you in having these tests performed. The results of genetic testing may be a significant scientific contribution to the understanding of whether or not people who have or develop elevated LDL and CRP are at risk of developing atherosclerosis; and may help serve as a guide to future treatment of patients.

Test results will be kept confidential in accordance with all applicable laws. To ensure participant confidentiality, these additional study samples will be coded with separate participant identifiers during the course of the study and will be rendered fully anonymous after the study has been completed. None of the test results will be provided to *you*, any insurance company, your employer, your family, *the investigator*, or *any other physician who is treating you or may treat you in the future*. You should be aware that the study sponsor has no obligation to conduct additional testing or notify *you*, *the investigator*, *your physician*, or any third party of any test results.

The blood samples collected in this study, the results of any genetic testing, any genetic sequences, cell lines, patents, diagnostic tests, drugs, and biological products developed directly or indirectly as a result of this study, as well as any information derived directly or indirectly from those samples, are the sole property of the study sponsor (and its successors, licensees, and assigns) and may be used for commercial purposes. You have no right to this property or to any share of the profits that may be earned directly or indirectly as a result of this study.

Participation in this part of the study is optional and entirely up to you. You will receive the same treatment and care under the study protocol whether or not you decide to provide a sample for genetic testing as described in this section. If you decide to participate, no additional blood samples will be collected. Plasma and buffy coat samples

obtained at Visit 2, in addition to being used for cholesterol, CRP and safety evaluations, will be stored for genetic testing.

I have read and I understand this section.

I consent to provide a blood sample under the conditions described in this section.

_____	_____	_____
Printed Name	Signature	Date

I do not consent to provide a blood sample under the conditions described in this section.

_____	_____	_____
Printed Name	Signature	Date

_____	_____	_____
Printed Name of Person	Signature of Person	Date
Administering this Consent	Administering this Consent	

Clinical Study Protocol: Appendix C

Study Code 4522US/0011

Version No. 2.0

Appendix Date 15 January, 2003

Appendix C

Declaration of Helsinki

Recommendations guiding physicians in biomedical research involving human subjects.

Adopted by the 18th World Medical Assembly, Helsinki, Finland, June 1964, amended by the 29th World Medical Assembly, Tokyo, Japan, October 1975 and the 35th World Medical Assembly, Venice, Italy, October 1983 and the 41st World Medical Assembly Hong Kong, September 1989 and the 48th General Assembly, Somerset West, Republic of South Africa, October 1996.

Introduction

It is the mission of the physician to safeguard the health of the people. His or her knowledge and conscience are dedicated to the fulfilment of this mission.

The Declaration of Geneva of The World Medical Association binds the physician with the words, "The health of my patient will be my first consideration," and the International Code of Medical Ethics declares that, "A physician shall act only in the patient's interest when providing medical care which might have the effect of weakening the physical and mental condition of the patient".

The purpose of biomedical research involving human subjects must be to improve diagnostic, therapeutic and prophylactic procedures and the understanding of the aetiology and pathogenesis of disease.

In current medical practice most diagnostic, therapeutic or prophylactic procedures involve hazards. This applies especially to biomedical research.

Medical progress is based on research which ultimately must rest in part on experimentation involving human subjects.

In the field of biomedical research a fundamental distinction must be recognised between medical research in which the aim is essentially diagnostic or therapeutic for a patient, and medical research, the essential object of which is purely scientific and without implying direct diagnostic or therapeutic value to the person subjected to the research.

Special caution must be exercised in the conduct of research which may affect the environment, and the welfare of animals used for research must be respected.

Because it is essential that the results of laboratory experiments be applied to human beings to further scientific knowledge and to help suffering humanity, the World Medical Association has prepared the following recommendations as a guide to every physician in biomedical research involving human subjects. They should be kept under review in the future. It must be stressed that the standards as drafted are only a guide to physicians all over the world. Physicians are not relieved from criminal, civil and ethical responsibilities under the laws of their own countries.

I. Basic principles

1. Biomedical research involving human subjects must conform to generally accepted scientific principles and should be based on adequately performed laboratory and animal experimentation and on a thorough knowledge of the scientific literature.
2. The design and performance of each experimental procedure involving human subjects should be clearly formulated in an experimental protocol which should be transmitted for consideration, comment and guidance to a specially appointed committee independent of the investigator and the sponsor provided that this independent committee is in conformity with the laws and regulations of the country in which the research experiment is performed.
3. Biomedical research involving human subjects should be conducted only by scientifically qualified persons and under the supervision of a clinically competent medical person. The responsibility for the human subject must always rest with a medically qualified person and never rest on the subject of the research, even though the subject has given his or her consent.

4. Biomedical research involving human subjects cannot legitimately be carried out unless the importance of the objective is in proportion to the inherent risk to the subject.
5. Every biomedical research project involving human subjects should be preceded by careful assessment of predictable risks in comparison with foreseeable benefits to the subject or to others. Concern for the interests of the subject must always prevail over the interests of science and society.
6. The right of the research subject to safeguard his or her integrity must always be respected. Every precaution should be taken to respect the privacy of the subject and to minimise the impact of the study on the subject's physical and mental integrity and on the personality of the subject.
7. Physicians should abstain from engaging in research projects involving human subjects unless they are satisfied that the hazards involved are believed to be predictable. Physicians should cease any investigation if the hazards are found to outweigh the potential benefits.
8. In publication of the results of his or her research, the physician is obliged to preserve the accuracy of the results. Reports of experimentation not in accordance with the principles laid down in this Declaration should not be accepted for publication.
9. In any research on human beings, each potential subject must be adequately informed of the aims, methods, anticipated benefits and potential hazards of the study and the discomfort it may entail. He or she should be informed that he or she is at liberty to abstain from participation in the study and that he or she is free to withdraw his or her consent to participation at any time. The physician should then obtain the subject's freely-given informed consent, preferably in writing.
10. When obtaining informed consent for the research project the physician should be particularly cautious if the subject is in a dependent relationship to him or her or may consent under duress. In that case the informed consent should be obtained by a physician who is not engaged in the investigation and who is completely independent of this official relationship.
11. In case of legal incompetence, informed consent should be obtained from the legal guardian in accordance with national legislation. Where physical or mental incapacity makes it impossible to obtain informed consent, or when the subject is a minor, permission from the responsible relative replaces that of the subject in accordance with national legislation.

Whenever the minor child is in fact able to give a consent, the minor's consent must be obtained in addition to the consent of the minor's legal guardian.

12. The research protocol should always contain a statement of the ethical considerations involved and should indicate that the principles enunciated in the present Declaration are complied with.

II. Medical research combined with professional care (Clinical research)

1. In the treatment of the sick person, the physician must be free to use a new diagnostic and therapeutic measure, if in his or her judgement it offers hope of saving life, re-establishing health or alleviating suffering.
2. The potential benefits, hazards and discomfort of a new method should be weighed against the advantages of the best current diagnostic and therapeutic methods.
3. In any medical study, every patient - including those of a control group, if any - should be assured of the best proven diagnostic and therapeutic method. This does not exclude the use of inert placebo studies where no proven diagnostic or therapeutic method exists.
4. The refusal of the patient to participate in a study must never interfere with the physician-patient relationship.
5. If the physician considers it essential not to obtain informed consent, the specific reasons for this proposal should be stated in the experimental protocol for transmission to the independent committee (1,2).
6. The physician can combine medical research with professional care, the objective being the acquisition of new medical knowledge, only to the extent that medical research is justified by its potential diagnostic or therapeutic value for the patient.

III. Non-therapeutic biomedical re-search involving human subjects

(Non-clinical biomedical research)

1. In the purely scientific application of medical research carried out on a human being, it is the duty of the physician to remain the protector of the life and health of that person on whom biomedical research is being carried out.
2. The subjects should be volunteers - either healthy persons or patients for whom the experimental design is not related to the patient's illness.
3. The investigator or the investigating team should discontinue the research if in his/her or their judgement it may, if continued, be harmful to the individual.
4. In research on man, the interest of science and society should never take precedence over considerations related to the well-being of the subject.

Clinical Study Protocol: Appendix D

Study Code 4522US/0011

Version No. 2.0

Appendix date 15 January, 2003

Appendix D

Investigators and study administrative structure

STAFF AT INVESTIGATIONAL SITE(S)

-List available upon request

ASTRAZENECA STUDY PERSONNEL

- List available upon request

DATA MONITORING OR SAFETY COMMITTEE(S)

- List available upon request

OTHER PARTICIPANTS

- List available upon request

Clinical Study Protocol: Appendix E

Study Code 4522US/0011

Version No. 2.0

Appendix date 15 January, 2003

Appendix E

Insurance and indemnity

INSURANCE AND INDEMNITY

AstraZeneca's liability is covered by a liability insurance policy with AstraZeneca Insurance Company Limited, policy No.: L/702938.

With respect to any liability directly or indirectly caused by the investigational products in connection with this Clinical Study, AstraZeneca assumes liability by law on behalf of the investigator(s) and his assistants for possible injury to the subject provided the investigator(s) and his assistants have followed the instructions of AstraZeneca in accordance with this protocol and any amendments thereto, that the investigational products administered to the subject in this Clinical Study have been supplied by AstraZeneca and that the investigator and his assistants have in general performed this clinical study in accordance with scientific practice and currently acceptable techniques and know-how.

AstraZeneca can forward a letter of indemnity if needed by the investigator(s)/institution.

Clinical Study protocol: Appendix F

Study Code 4522US/0011

Version No. 2.0

Appendix date 15 January, 2003

Appendix F

Additional safety information

1. FURTHER GUIDANCE ON THE DEFINITION OF A SERIOUS ADVERSE EVENT (SAE)

Life threatening

'Life-threatening' means that the subject was at immediate risk of death from the adverse event as it occurred or it is suspected that use or continued use of the product would result in the subject's death. 'Life-threatening' does not mean that had an adverse event occurred in a more severe form it might have caused death (ie hepatitis that resolved without hepatic failure).

Hospitalisation

Out-subject treatment in an emergency room is not in itself a serious adverse event, although the reasons for it may be (eg, bronchospasm, laryngeal oedema). Hospital admissions and/or surgical operations planned before or during a study are not considered adverse events if the illness or disease existed before the subject was enrolled in the study, provided that it did not deteriorate in an unexpected way during the study.

Important medical event or medical intervention

Medical and scientific judgement should be exercised in deciding whether a case is serious in a situation where important medical events may not be immediately life-threatening or result in death, hospitalisation, disability or incapacity but may jeopardise the subject or may require medical intervention to prevent one or more outcomes listed in the definition of serious. These should usually be considered as serious. Examples of such events are:

- Angioedema not severe enough to require intubation but requiring iv. hydrocortisone treatment
- Hepatotoxicity caused by paracetamol (acetaminophen) overdose requiring treatment with N-acetylcysteine
- Intensive treatment in an emergency room or at home for allergic bronchospasm
- Blood dyscrasias (eg, neutropenia or anaemia requiring blood transfusion, etc.) or convulsions that do not result in hospitalisation
- Development of drug dependency or drug abuse

2. FURTHER GUIDANCE ON THE ASSESSMENT OF CAUSALITY

The following factors should be considered when deciding if there is a “reasonable possibility” that an adverse event (AE) may have been caused by the investigational product.

- **Time course of events and exposure to suspect drug.** Has the subject actually received the suspect drug? Did the AE occur in a reasonable temporal relationship to the administration of suspect drug?
- **Consistency with known drug profile.** Was the AE consistent with the previous knowledge of the suspect drug (pharmacology and toxicology) or drugs of the same pharmacological class? OR could the AE be anticipated from its pharmacological properties?
- **Dechallenge experience.** Did the AE resolve or improve on stopping or reducing the dose of the suspect drug?
- **No alternative cause.** The AE cannot be reasonably explained by another aetiology such as the underlying disease, other drugs, other host or environmental factors.
- **Rechallenge experience.** Did the AE reoccur if the suspected drug was reintroduced after having been stopped? AstraZeneca would not normally recommend or support a rechallenge.
- **Laboratory tests.** Has a specific laboratory investigation confirmed the relationship?

A “reasonable possibility” could be considered to exist for an AE where one or more of these factors exist.

In contrast, there would not be a “reasonable possibility” of causality if none of the above criteria apply or where there is evidence of exposure and a reasonable time course but any dechallenge (if performed) is negative or ambiguous or there is another more likely cause of the AE.

In difficult cases, other factors could be considered such as:

- Is this a recognised feature of overdose of the drug?
- Is there a known mechanism

Ambiguous cases should be considered as being a “reasonable possibility” of a causal relationship unless further evidence becomes available to refute this.

Clinical Study protocol: Appendix G

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Appendix date 15 January, 2003

Appendix G
Management of Elevated Liver Enzymes

MANAGEMENT OF ELEVATED LIVER ENZYMES

1. Subjects who develop increased transaminases should be monitored until the abnormalities resolve according to investigator's clinical judgement
2. Should an increase in ALT $> 3 \times$ ULN occur on 2 consecutive measurements, withdrawal of trial therapy is recommended